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Annotation: *this article will talk about the need to understand the identity of the nation, to show its specific national values and traditions, the culture and ancient history of each nation is embodied above all in its oral creativity – folk art, Epic and epic.*

Base words: *folk creativity, creativity, upbringing, folklore, cultural centers, festival, public holiday, audition.*

Folk creativity is the artistic, creative-practical and amateur activity of the people's masses. These include folk oral art of traditional material and intangible culture (folklore), folk music (musical folklore), folk theater (performance art), folk games (dance), puppetry, Doric and wooden leg games (folk circus), folk fine and applied decorative art, and types of creativity such as technical and artistic amateurism. The types of folk creativity with the participation of many in the creation and creative process were formed in accordance with the level of folk lifestyle, living conditions, social Labor, passed from generation to generation, from teacher to disciple, constantly perfected, increasingly traditional, and, finally, with the characteristic of professionalism (professionalism), live performance conditions and daily practice have reached US. A number of ancient examples of folk art have been preserved in written sources, in the works of historians and writers, in rockeries, in monuments of Archaeology and architecture, in household items. The examples of folk creativity are expressed in the way of life of the people, social and domestic life, labor activity, views on nature and society, beliefs and religious visions, their history in relation to man and the world, their artistic world, their level of knowledge, their ideas about a happy and just time.

To promote folk oral creativity, 837 cultural centers operate in our country today, which serve as the main foundation for the development of amateur art. There are a total of 4,522 circles in these cultural centers with 52,970 amateurs. Of this, 37,340 are young people. Cultural centers have 482 teams with the title of people's amateur, with a total of more than 5,000 amateurs participating in these teams. In this sense, it is important to improve the activities of cultural centers, to create the necessary conditions for them. To date, 367 cultural centers have been renovated and put into use. The program of measures approved by the decree of our president of May 26, 2020

In paragraph 25, the Ministry of Culture is tasked to build, reconstruct, overhaul and equip new buildings for cultural centers.

The scientific and methodological center of people's creativity and cultural and educational affairs of the Republic is engaged in the development, promotion of various directions of people's creativity in Uzbekistan, Organization of various examinations, festivals and public holidays in the field of people's creativity. Uzbekistan regularly hosts folkloric ethnographic communities, askiks and curiosities, Republican competitions of wedding-ceremony song performers, National drugstores, Republican competitions of traditional circus arts and amateur puppet theaters, the International Open Folklore Festival "Boysun spring" and many festivals.

In conclusion, the long – standing history and culture of any people is most primarily embodied in his oral creativity-folk art, Epic and Epics, which are an invaluable resource for the realization of the identity of the nation, the preservation and development of its specific national values and traditions.

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